

Mixed Polymesomorphism

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Mixed nematic mesomorphism in the binary systems wherein one or both the constituents are nematic mesomorphs has been reported¹⁻⁷. Some binary systems have also been investigated for the mixed smectic mesomorphism⁸. Recently some work has been done on the effect of dissolution of a non-liquid crystalline substance on the mesomorphs displaying a smectic—nematic transformation^{9,10}. Here we present the preliminary observations of our investigation of mixed mesomorphism in binary systems comprising *p-n*-octyloxy

TABLE

Component A : *p-n*-octyloxybenzoic acid (*L.C.*). Solid 101°, Smectic 108°, Nematic 148.5° mixed with Isotropic.

Component B	M.P. °C	Eutectic Mol % A	Temp. °C	Extent of mixed polyemesomorphism			
				Smectic—Nematic		Nematic—Isotropic	
				Mol % A	Temp.°C	Mol % A	Temp.°C
1. <i>p</i> -Toluic acid	177.0	79.5	74.0	96.5 (83.0)	99.0 (78.0)	46.5	133.0
2. <i>p</i> -Methoxybenzoic acid	184.0	88.5	84.0	88.0 (84.5)	85.0 (81.0)	49.0 (38.0)	147.0 (148.0)
3. <i>p</i> -Ethoxybenzoic acid	196.0	88.0	80.0	87.0 (84.0)	84.0 (80.0)	57.5 (50.0)	154.0 (155.0)
4. <i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoic acid	236.0	81.0	90.0	88.0 (83.0)	93.0 (88.0)	74.0 (70.0)	145.0 (144.0)
5. <i>p</i> -Bromobenzoic acid	251.0	87.0	97.0	90.0 (87.0)	97.6 (94.0)	81.5 (76.0)	146.0 (145.0)
9. <i>p</i> -Iodobenzoic acid	269.0	90.5	89.5	90.5 (80.0)	99.0 (97.0)	87.0 (79.5)	146.0 (144.0)
7. <i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	241.0	84.0	81.0	78.0	120.0	64.5 (52.0)	173.0 (184.0)

The figures in parenthesis represent the mole percentage and transition temperature for the monotropic behaviour.

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benzoic acid, a polymesomorph exhibiting smectic-nematic transformation, the other non-liquid crystalline constituents being *p*-substituted benzoic acids. The melting points, transition temperatures and eutectic temperatures of the systems are summarized in the Table.

Dave *et al.*⁸ who studied the systems comprising a pure smectic component and a non-mesomorphic component observed that the presence of —NO₂ group enhances the smectic mesophase in the mixed liquid crystals. Dave *et al.*⁹ also studied the systems comprising a polymesomorph exhibiting smectic-nematic mesophases and a non-mesomorph. In this case they observed that the presence of the —NO₂ group not only shows a maximum in the smectic mesophase but the nematic mesophase is eliminated in the mixed polymesomorphism. Recently Shroeder and Shroeder¹⁰ studied systems comprising a polymesomorph exhibiting smectic-nematic mesophases and a non-mesomorph. They report that the presence of NO₂ group enhances both the mesophases in the mixed polymesomorphism. The results of the present study are also indicative of the enhancing effect of the presence of the nitro group on both smectic and nematic mesophases of the polymesomorph. Further work is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Ethoxybenzoic acid and *p*-*n*-octyloxybenzoic acid were synthesised by the method of Jones¹¹ while other *p*-substituted benzoic acids were B.D.H. products.

The binary mixtures were investigated with the help of Leitz Ortholux Polarizing Microscope equipped with heating arrangement¹².

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